
INSTITUTIONAL SOFTWARE TEMPLATES FOR ALIGNING BEST PRACTICES IN RESEARCH SOFTWARE

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WELCOME TO THIS WORKSHOP!

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OBJECTIVE OF THIS WORKSHOP

- Discuss the role of software templates in adhering to best practices when developing research software.
- Discuss the importance of coordinating efforts to define best practices for research software.

FAIR PRINCIPLES

Findable

Accessible

Interoperable

Reusable

OBJECTIVE OF THIS WORKSHOP

- Expectations from participants
 - How important is the role of best practices in creating high quality software?
 - And how do we coordinate the **efforts on best practices**, so that research software has **similar quality standards**?
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**WHAT IS YOUR JOB POSITION/
ROLE?**

HOW MUCH EXPERIENCE DO YOU HAVE IN WRITING (RESEARCH) SOFTWARE?

*Software that was developed for research purposes- support, enable, or perform research.

RESEARCH SOFTWARE TEMPLATES

A research software template provides the structure and boilerplate code for a research software project*

- Code and resource layout
- Version control
- License
- Citation
- Documentation
- Code documentation
- Packaging
- Unit testing
- Publishing

• ...

Illustration by Storyset.com

├── LICENSE	<- Open-source license if
├── Makefile	<- Makefile with convenient
├── README.md	<- The top-level README fo
├── data	
│ ├── external	<- Data from third party s
│ ├── interim	<- Intermediate data that
│ ├── processed	<- The final, canonical da
│ └── raw	<- The original, immutable
├── docs	<- A default mkdocs projec
├── models	<- Trained and serialized
├── notebooks	<- Jupyter notebooks. Nam
	the creator's initials
	`1.0-jqp-initial-data-6
├── pyproject.toml	<- Project configuration f
	{{ cookiecutter.module
├── references	<- Data dictionaries, manu
├── reports	<- Generated analysis as H
│ └── figures	<- Generated graphics and
├── requirements.txt	<- The requirements file f
	generated with `pip fre

WHY USE A RESEARCH SOFTWARE TEMPLATE?

- Facilitates the initiation of research software projects by reducing time and lowering entry barriers.
 - Encourages the use of best practices- addition of licenses, version control, documentation
 - Supports adherence to FAIR principles- findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable.
 - Promotes standardized and consistent structures across projects
 - Makes it easier to adopt evolving software development best practices in a fast-changing field
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GROUP ACTIVITY

INTRODUCE YOURSELF TO YOUR GROUP

- Share your name and which discipline you work in.
 - Have you ever used a software template? If so, in what context?
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GROUP DISCUSSION

What are elements that a software template should have?

**WHITEBOARD SESSION-
PASTE YOUR WRITTEN
ELEMENTS ON THE BOARD**

WHITEBOARD SESSION- DISCUSS SOFTWARE TEMPLATE ELEMENTS TOGETHER

- Are there elements that each group has in common?
 - What distinct elements did each group choose?
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META-TEMPLATE

META-TEMPLATE

Meta-Template for Research Software

Best practices for sustainable
research software

- Developed under the national project ‘Best Practices for Sustainable Software’.
- The meta template helps facilitate creation of templates with common core elements such as license files, basic readme, etc.
- The user can then customize the template to add language or discipline specific elements and tweak existing common elements.
- The resulting template can then be used to create research software.

	Language specific components
	Components from meta template

	Language specific components
	Components from meta template

META-TEMPLATE VIDEO DEMONSTRATION

https://youtu.be/z-bmsxxQV6o?si=HTb2HXMHTjDO_KwO

**DISCUSSION- IS A TASK FORCE
NEEDED FOR COORDINATION OF
EFFORTS ON BEST PRACTICES?**

**AT WHAT LEVEL SHOULD SUCH A TASK FORCE
BE IMPLEMENTED?**

THANK YOU !

Please, take a card if you plan to check the tool after this event, or if you would like to suggest someone you know to try out the tool.

Take one card for each case.

 **Meta-Template
for Research Software**

Software templates
to guide best
practices in
research software

 ITC